

YELLOW MOSAIC IN GRAPEVINE: AN OVERVIEW OF THE MOLECULAR AND CYTOLOGICAL CHANGES ELICITED DURING THE SYNDROME THROUGH RNA-SEQ AND ELECTRON MICROSCOPY INVESTIGATIONS

Giusy D'Attoma¹, Amani Ben Slimen², Angelo de Stradis¹, Massimiliano Morelli¹, Toufic Elbeaino², Giorgio Gambino³, Michele Digiaro², Michela Chiumentì¹, Angelantonio Minafra¹

¹Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection - National Research Council; ²Agronomic Mediterranean Institute - CIHEAM; ³Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection - National Research Council; E-mail: giusy.dattoma@cnr.it

ABSTRACT:

Yellow mosaic (YM) in grapevine is associated to systemic infection of grapevine fanleaf virus (GFLV; species *Nepovirus foliumflabelli*). The syndrome is characterized by a persistent yellow discoloration of the leaves that occurs during spring and summer on multiple branches of the vine, while others may remain normally pigmented. Such yellowing reverts to a normal green by late summer, and it could be accompanied by typical leaf deformities and degeneration caused by GFLV. Although various grapevine cultivars consistently exhibit the same phenotype over the years, serological and molecular techniques are unable to differentiate between different GFLV isolates or variants. In this context, three YM-affected vines were selected in Apulia vineyards (Italy) and sampled in both green and yellow leaf tissues. Total RNAs were submitted for sequencing (mRNA and smallRNA). Quality-checked reads were assembled with rnaSPAdes, then annotated using BLAST. The virome analysis detected the presence of viral agents commonly affecting grapevine, without showing a discrimination pattern between yellow and green leaf tissues. GFLV showed a higher genome coverage than the other viruses, with the isolate sequence correlated with the source plant accession, not with the symptom. In addition, RT-qPCR of GFLV demonstrated that its titer was similar in both leaf tissues. More than 3500 statistically significant differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were identified, with about 1400 genes overexpressed in the yellow leaf tissues, and over than 2100 underexpressed in the same tissues. GO enrichment of the related DEGs revealed a higher transcriptional activity, ethylene-activated signaling pathways and chloroplast/photosynthesis-related proteins in green tissues, whilst yellow leaf tissues were characterized by an increased metabolism of carbohydrates. About 30 DEGs were selected for validation by RT-qPCR. Genes showing the highest fold-change values in both leaf tissues were also used in a monthly analysis, from May to September, conducted on the same vines. Differentially expressed miRNAs were also consistently validated. Finally, a noteworthy result was the chloroplast analysis in EM. In YM leaf tissues, chloroplasts showed a strong alteration of the thylakoids' membrane organization. These alterations range from a complete lack of thylakoids to vesiculations of the thylakoid's membrane, compatible with their evolution into gerontoplasts.

KEYWORDS: yellow mosaic; grapevine; grapevine fanleaf virus

16th ISPVE

International Symposium of
Plant Virus Epidemiology

June 30th to July 3rd, 2025

Cásper Líbero | São Paulo - BR

Scientific Proceedings

Promoted By

Hosted By

